

Saint Thecla (acts of Paul and Thecla) and baptism

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Thecla is a young woman who is engaged to a man named Thamyris and is about to get married. One day, while listening to Paul's preaching about the value and virtue of male and female virginity in a Christian context, Thecla was moved by his words. She was so inspired that she wanted to remain a virgin forever. When Thamyris discovers her intentions, he asks for Paul's persecution. Thecla followed Paul to prison and continued listening to his teachings. However, when she revealed her desire to remain a virgin in public, she was also persecuted, and the local authorities ordered her execution. Thecla was not yet baptized; however, her soul was seeking baptism, and she asked Paul several times for it. During the time of Antiquity, Christian baptism was a simple ritual that was performed on a daily basis. John's baptism was a clear example of this, as more and more Christians were baptized in the name of the Father, the Son, and the Holy Spirit. However, Thecla's experience suggests that this was not always the case. As a catechumen, she had to strive to achieve baptism on her own, which was a difficult and challenging process. While it is unclear why she was not baptized, her journey as a catechumen provides valuable insights into the early Christian church's beliefs and practices. Thecla eventually was baptized on her own before her last conviction. This act reveals many myths about the act and ritual of baptism. As far as we know, the ritual of baptism was performed by a priest or the Baptist in Late Antiquity; Thecla comes to erase this thought and fact and tells us that baptism is a personal ritual that anyone with true faith inside them can perform. Of course, what Thecla did was not a popular option but rather an emergency one. Emergency baptism was not that popular in the first century since the establishment of Christianity was not that stable yet. Still, it certainly existed and was performed by the laic.

Date Range: 1 CE - 2 CE

Region: Asia Minor

Region tags: Asia Minor

Where Pauline Christ groups were located approx.
50-62 CE

Status of Readership:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources and Corpora

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Translation, in Elliott, J.K. *The Apocryphal New Testament: A Collection of Apocryphal Christian Literature in an English Translation*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. 1993
- Source 2: Karavidopoulos I. *Απόκρυφα Χριστιανικά Κείμενα Β΄. Απόκρυφες Πράξεις, Επιστολές, Αποκαλύψεις*, Thessaloniki: Pournaras 2004.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/list-of-books-of-the-New-Testament-2175367>
- Source 1 Description: New Testament books

Online Corpora

Relevant online Primary Textual Corpora (original languages and/or translations)

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/list-of-books-of-the-New-Testament-2175367>
- Source 1 Description: New Testament

General Variables

Materiality

Methods of Composition

- Written

Inked

- without Ink

Medium upon which the text is written/incised

- Papyrus

Was the material modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Was the text modified before the writing or incising process?

- Physical preparation

Location

Is the text stored in a specific location?

[Note at which point in time, for reference, if known; select all that apply]

- I don't know

Is the location where the text stored accompanied by iconography or images?

- I don't know

Is the area where the text is stored accompanied by an-iconic images?

– I don't know

Production & Intended Audience

Production

Is the production of the text funded by the polity?

– No

Is the text considered official religious scripture?

– No

Written in distinctly religious/sacred language?

– No

Intended Audience

What is the estimated number of people considered to be the audience of the text

This should be the total number of people who would serve as the intended audience for the text.

– I don't know

Does the Religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members?

– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing mandated according to the text?

– No

↳ Is proselytizing encouraged according to the text?

– No

↳ Are there specific rewards for proselytizing according to the text?

– Yes

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for religious professionals?

– No

↳ Are rewards for proselytizing promised by the text for all adherents?
– Yes

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for religious professionals?
– No

↳ Are rewards for missionary work promised by the text for all adherents?
– No

↳ Is proselytizing by coercion acceptable according to the text?
– No

↳ Is textual justification for proselytizing part of the norm in the religious group?
– No

↳ Is the text silent on matters of proselytization?
– Yes

↳ Does proselytization take place regardless of the fact that the text is silent on the matter?
– Yes

↳ Is proselytizing forbidden or restricted by the text?
– No

Are there clear reformist movements?

(Reformism, as in not proselytizing to potential new conservative, but "conversion" - or rather, reform - to the "correct interpretation"?)

– No

Is the text in question employed in ritual practice?

– No

Is there material significance to the text?

– No

Context and Content of the Text (Beliefs and Practices)

Context

Is the text itself accompanied by art?

– No

Are there multiple versions of the text?

– No

Is the text part of a collection of texts?

– Yes

↳ Is there a sense of canonization?

– No

↳ Is the text part of a series of volumes?

– No

If the text is not explicitly scripture, is it part of another important literary tradition?

– Yes

↳ Cultural with religious implications?

– Yes

↳ Behavioral literature?

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Apocryphal literature

Content

Is the text - or does the text include - a ritual list, manual, bibliography, index, or vocabulary?
(Select all that apply)

–Other [specify]: No

Are there lineages or a single lineage established by the text?

– No

Does the text express a formal legal code?

– No

Formulating a specifically religious calendar?

– No

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present in the text?

– No

Is belief in an afterlife indicated in the text?

– Yes

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Is the temporality of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group?

– No

Is there debate in the interpretation of the language of the afterlife?

– No

Is belief in reincarnation in this world specified in the text?

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text indicate if co-sacrifices should be present in burials?

– No

Does the text specify grave goods for burial?

– No

Are formal burials present in the text?

– No

Are there practices that have funerary associations presented in the text?

– No

Are supernatural beings present in the text?

– No

Previously human spirits are present

– No

Non-human supernatural beings are present

– No

Does the text attest to a pantheon of supernatural beings?

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present according to the text?

– No

Is there a supernatural being that is physically present in the/as a result of the text?

– Yes

Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god visible to anyone in the text?

– No

Is the aspect of the supernatural being/high god hidden from anyone in the text?

– No

Are other categories of beings present?

–Other [specify]: No

Does the text guide divination practices?

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment in the text?

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards in the text?

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present in the text?

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– Yes

↳ Alive, identified

– Yes

↳ Coming in this lifetime

– Yes

↳ Coming on a specified date

– Yes

↳ Coming in unspecified time in near future

– No

↳ Coming in unspecified time in distant future

– No

↳ Coming has already passed

– Yes

↳ One in a line of many past and future messiahs

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known?

– Yes

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions

– Yes

↳ Other purpose

– Specify: Love, unity, Belief in God

Is an eschatology present in the text?

– No

Norms & Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the text?

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious text?

– Yes

↳ What is the nature of this distinction?

– Strongly present & highlighted

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the text?

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to (select all that apply)

– All individuals within society

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the text?

– Yes

↳ Honesty/trustworthiness/integrity

– No

– No

↳ Courage (in battle)

– No

↳ Courage (generic)

– No

↳ Compassion/empathy/kindness/benevolence

– No

↳ Mercy/forgiveness/tolerance

– Yes

↳ Generosity/charity

– No

↳ Selflessness/selfless giving

– Yes

↳ Righteousness/moral rectitude

– No

↳ Ritual purity/ritual adherence/abstention from sources of impurity

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness/courtesy

– No

↳ Familial obedience/filial piety

– No

- ↳ Fidelity/loyalty
 - No
- ↳ Cooperation
 - No
- ↳ Independence/creativity/freedom
 - Yes
- ↳ Moderation/frugality
 - No
- ↳ Forbearance/fortitude/patience
 - Yes
- ↳ Diligence/self-discipline/excellence
 - No
- ↳ Assertiveness/decisiveness/confidence/initiative
 - No
- ↳ Strength (physical)
 - No
- ↳ Power/status/nobility
 - No
- ↳ Humility/modesty
 - No
- ↳ Contentment/serenity/equanimity
 - No
- ↳ Joyfulness/enthusiasm/cheerfulness
 - No

- ↳ Optimism/hope
 - No
- ↳ Gratitude/thankfulness
 - No
- ↳ Reverence/awe/wonder
 - No
- ↳ Faith/belief/trust/devotion
 - Yes
- ↳ Wisdom/understanding
 - Yes
- ↳ Discernment/intelligence
 - No
- ↳ Beauty/attractiveness
 - No
- ↳ Cleanliness (physical)/orderliness
 - No
- ↳ Other important virtues
 - Yes

Advocacy of Practices

Does the text require celibacy (full sexual abstinence)?

– Yes

Does the text require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence)?

– No

Does the text require castration?

– No

Does the text require fasting?

– No

Does the text require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods)?

– No

Does the text require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations?

– Yes

Does the text require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of adults?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of children?

– No

Does the text require self-sacrifice (suicide)?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of property/valuable items?

– No

Does the text require sacrifice of time (e.g. attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.)?

– No

Does the text require physical risk taking?

– Yes

Does the text require accepting ethical precepts?

– Yes

Does the text require marginalization by out-group members?

– No

Does the text require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household)?

– No

Does the text require participation in large-scale rituals?

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present as indicated in the text?

– No

Does the text employ fictive kinship terminology?

– No

Does the text include elements that are intended to be entertaining?

– No

Does the text specify sacrifices, offerings, and maintenance of a sacred space?

– No

Institutions & Production Environment of Text

Society & Institutions

Society of religious group that produced the text is best characterized as:

– A House Society

Are there specific elements of society that have controlled the reproduction of the text?

– Other

Notes: Small community

Are there specific elements of society involved with the destruction of the text?

– A House Society

Welfare

Does the text specify institutionalized famine relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized poverty relief?

– No

Does the text specify institutionalized care for elderly & infirm?

– No

Other forms of welfare?

– No

Education

Are there formal educational institutions available for teaching the text?

– No

Are there formal educational institutions specified according to the text?

– No

Does the text make provisions for non-religious education?

– No

Does the text restrict education to religious professionals?

– No

Does the text restrict education among religious professionals?

– No

Is education gendered according to the text?

– No

Is education gendered with respect to this text and larger textual tradition?

– No

Does the text specify teaching relationships or ratios? (i.e.: 1:20; 1:1)

– No

Are there specific relationships to teachers that are advocated by the text?

– No

Are there worldly rewards/benefits to education according to the text specified by the text itself?

– No

Bureaucracy

Is bureaucracy regulated by this text?

– No

Public Works

Does the text detail interaction with public works?

– No

Taxation

Does the text specify forms of taxation?

– No

Warfare

Does the text mention warfare?

– No

Food Production

Does the text mentioned food production/disbursement?

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Saint Thecla (acts of Paul and Thecla) and baptism, Jensen, R.. Living Water. Images, Symbols,

and Settings of Early Christian Baptism. Leiden: Brill, 2010.

Reference: Saint Thecla (acts of Paul and Thecla) and baptism, "Lester K. Little(editor). *plague and the End of Antiquity: The Pandemic of 541-750*. Xiv + 360 Pp., Bibl., Index. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2007. \$75 (cloth)." 98, no. 4 (December 2007). <https://doi.org/10.1086/529355>.

Reference: Saint Thecla (acts of Paul and Thecla) and baptism, Elliot, J.K.. *The Apocryphal New Testament: A Collection of Apocryphal Christian Literature in an English Translation*. Oxford University Press, 2007.

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